
Quality Analysis of Implementation of Cleaner Production at Batik Industry Using The Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) Methods as a Waste Management Tool

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Abstract

The implementation of cleaner production must be implemented in order to protect the environment due to an increase in the quantity of batik waste due to the increasingly rapid growth of batik industry. Batik industry needs to measure and analyze the extent to which the production process has implemented cleaner production and evaluates its shortcomings for future improvements. In this study the calculation using the Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) method is applied to determine the importance and performance of the batik group industry at Sleman Regency. This approach aims to assist the batik industry group in evaluating of implementation of their cleaner production in the production process so that from the integration it can be seen what needs to be prioritized to be improved as a corrective action. From the research results, several corrective actions, waste management, water minimization and the reused wax process can be continued to be a corrective action.

Keywords: cleaner production, batik industry group, Importance Performance Analysis (IPA)

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1. Introduction

UNESCO has awarded that batik is Indonesia's national cultural heritage followed by an increase in the quantity of the batik industry and the growth of new batik industry centers. Batik industry sector has a strategic role in development especially to foster the level of employment and its contribution in encouraging national economic growth. Along with the increase in the batik industry, environmental problems are also increasing. These problems are mainly due to dissipation among other things in the production process which often results in waste of raw materials, water and energy and the disposal of waste that will burden the environment. Nowadays, the application of waste management tools leads to improve to minimize the emergence of an integrated and systematic manner by all interested parties towards achieving a balance of environmental, economic and social aspects. Because it is very necessary for a form of waste management equipment that can be applied to the batik industry,

considering it is a challenge to implement an appropriate waste management effort in small industries as batik industry.

One of the preventive waste management tool is the application of cleaner production. The term of cleaner production was introduced by the United Nation Environment Program (UNEP) in May 1989 and was formally submitted in September 1989 at a seminar on The Promotion of cleaner production at Canterbury. Indonesia agreed to adopt the definition conveyed by UNEP (2003) namely, cleaner production is a preventive and integrated environmental management strategy that is applied continuously to the production process, products and services so as to increase cleaner production and reduce the risk of human occurrence and environment. Therefore the strategy needs to be applied continuously to the production process and product life cycle with the aim of reducing risks to humans and the environment (Nastiti, 2009). Meanwhile, according to the United Nation Industrial Organization (UNIDO, 2002), adding that cleaner production is an environmental management strategy that is directed towards prevention and integration so that it can be applied throughout the production cycle. The two definitions above have the same goal, namely to increase productivity by providing a better level of efficiency in the use of raw materials or raw materials, energy, water and encourage better environmental performance through reducing generation of waste and emissions sources and reducing impacts products for the environment from the life cycle of products designed to be environmentally friendly and effective cost.

Before the concept of cleaner production began to be developed, initially environmental management was based on a carrying capacity approach due to the limited natural carrying capacity to neutralize increasing pollution. Efforts to overcome pollution problems change the approach of processing waste that is formed (end of pipe treatment). The concept of cleaner production is a concept that has a hierarchy where the principle of 5 (five) R (Rethink, Reduce, Reuse, Recycled, Recovery) must be done directly (in-pipe recycle). So that the resolution of environmental problems is emphasized at the source of pollution not at the end of the process such as the end-of-pipe treatment technology, including the efficient use of natural resources which also means shrinkage of waste produced, pollution, and risk reduction for human health and safety. This concept does not always require expensive or sophisticated technology but often results in potential savings that increase competitiveness in the market. What is needed is a change of attitude, responsible environmental management and assessment of technology choices.

Some of the concepts in the cleaner production strategy introduced in the batik industry include the following (Bohnet M, 2010):

- Reducing or minimizing the use of raw materials, water and energy and avoiding the use of hazard materials and reducing the formation of waste at the source, so that it prevents or reduces the problem of pollution and environmental damage and the risks to humans.
- Changes in patterns of production and consumption apply both to the process and the products produced, so it must be understood correctly the analysis of product life cycle.
- Cleaner production cannot be successfully implemented without any changes in mindset, attitudes and behavior of all parties involved both from the government, the community and the industrial world. Besides that, it is also necessary to apply management patterns among industry and government by considering environmental aspects.

- Implementation of environmentally friendly technology, management and standard operating procedures in accordance with established requirements. These activities do not always require high investment costs; even if they occur often the time needed to return capital investment is relatively short.
- The implementation of this cleaner production program is more directed at self-regulation and arrangements that are consensus-based or negotiated regulatory approach. So the implementation of a cleaner production program does not only rely on government regulations, but it is based on awareness of behavior change.

This paper will present an analysis of the measurement of the quality of the application of cleaner production in the Mantaran batik group and Ayu Arimbi batik group at Sleman Regency. The two batik group industries were chosen as partners in the implementation of cleaner production carried out between the Center for Crafts and Batik (BBKB) in collaboration with the Department of Industry and Trade of Sleman Regency. The basis for implementing the cleaner production program. It is because of the growth of the batik industry every year since the emergence of the Sleman batik motif which is the Sleman batik icon, the motif of "Parijoto Salak". Along with the development of these batik industries centers, there is concern about the potential for environmental pollution due to an increase in the quantity of batik waste. Then through the implementation of sustainable cleaner production, it is expected that the use of raw materials, the volume of waste water and utilization of energy can be reduced. This reduction will reduce costs production so that the batik industry in Sleman Regency can compete with other batik industries. The other important thing is to reduce the impact of environmental pollution and the health of workers and the community due to the production process in the batik industry.

The measurement of the quality of the application of cleaner production in the two industry groups was carried out by the Importance performance Analysis (IPA) method. IPA is a method that maps the perceptions of group members in each batik industry to the importance of aspects of the implementation of cleaner production by group members in each batik industry to performance aspects of the cleaner production program and to identify the applications that have been made in the batik industry and things that need to be improved. Science is a method used to analyze the relationship between importance and performance and the theory that the target level of performance of certain product attributes must be proportional to the interests of these attributes. In other words, interest is seen as a reaction from the relative values of various consumers attributes (Slack, 1990).

The data presented in the questionnaire are elaborated on the Likert scale as an indicator of size scale for the benefit according to members of the Mantaran batik group and batik group Ayu Arimbi Plalangan at Sleman Regency on the implementation or real performance of the program to implement cleaner production. Likert scale data is given a quantitative score to be used in calculations (Rangkuti, 2008), this concept actually originates from the SERVQUAL concept, essentially, as suggested by Parasuraman (Rangkuti, 2008) the level of importance of group members in each batik industry is measured in relation to what should be done by members of the Mantaran batik group and batik group Ayu Arimbi Plalangan at Sleman Regency.

Based on the results of the assessment of the level of importance and level of performance, calculations will be made regarding the level of importance and level of performance which is then

illustrated in a Cartesian diagram. The level of importance and performance contained in the Cartesian diagram is in the form of scores of importance assessment and total performance. Each attribute is positioned in a diagram. The total assessment of the level of performance shows the position of an attribute on the X axis while the position of the attribute on the Y axis is indicated by the total score of importance on the attribute. (Rangkuti, 2003). The horizontal axis (X) will be filled by the level of implementation score, while the upright axis (Y) will be filled by the importance level score. The principle of science calculation is carried out mapping into 4 quadrants for all variables that affect service quality. Distribution of quadrants in IPA can be seen in figure 1

Figure 1. Importance Performance Analysis Performance (IPA) Diagram

The strategies that can be carried out regarding the position of each variable in the four quarters can be explained as follows:

- This Quadrant 1 (Concentrate These) is an area that contains factors that are considered *important* by members of the batik group, but in reality these factors *are not in accordance* with the performance of members of the batik group (the level of satisfaction obtained is still low). The variables included in this quadrant must be increased.
- Quadrant 2 (Keep Up The Good Work) This is an area that contains factors that are considered *important* by members of the batik group, and the factors considered by members of the batik group are in accordance with what they feel so that the level of satisfaction is relatively higher.
- Quadrant 3 (Low Priority) is an area that contains factors that are considered less *important* by members of the batik group, and in reality the *performance* is not too special. The increase in variables included in this quadrant can be reconsidered because the effect on the benefits felt by members of the batik group is very small.
- Quadrant 4 (Possible Overkill) is a region that contains factors that are considered *less important* by members of the batik group and they are felt to be too excessive. The variables included in this quadrant can be reduced so that batik groups can implement cleaner production.

Based on the results of the measurement analysis using the IPA method, figures will be obtained which show the quality of the application of cleaner production in the two batik industries. Quantity data will present the gap value between the perceptions and expectations of members of the Mantaran batik group and Ayu Arimbi batik group after obtaining the implementation of a cleaner production program. The data can be used to propose for priority corrective actions that can be taken to improve the quality of the implementation of cleaner production in the Mantaran batik group and Ayu Arimbi batik group.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

The material in this study is a questionnaire in the form of a likert scale of interest based on attributes consisting of five-dimensional attributes of the implementation of a cleaner production program, namely the use of materials, hazardous waste, storage and handling of materials, water and waste water, energy, protection of occupational safety and health. This questionnaire consists of general data statements regarding the implementation of cleaner production which is carried out daily by the two batik industries above. In more detail the indicators are contained in the questions in the form of a questionnaire distributed to respondents, namely members of the second group of the batik industry in order to obtain answers related to the matter under study.

2.2. Method

2.2.1 Research Design

The research design in this paper is a type of survey research. In survey research, primary data collection methods provide questions to individual respondents. This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach based on user-approach, namely the approach that states that the program implemented has high quality is a program that satisfies user expectations. Therefore, the gap analysis model is specifically designed to see the gap between the expectations and perceptions of members of the Mantaran batik group and Ayu Arimbi batik group. This method is seen as a fairly appropriate model for analyzing and measuring the level of quality towards the application of cleaner production activities. While the IPA model can be seen there are two main attributes that determine user satisfaction, namely expectation and perceived performance. Expectation is the user's expectation of the desired product. While perceived performance is the perception of members of the batik industry group on their environmental performance. They measured through five dimensions of the quality of the application of cleaner production, namely the efficiency of the use of materials, waste materials or hazardous, storage and handling of materials, water and waste water, energy, protection of occupational safety and health.

Tabel 1. Dimensions and variables of cleaner production program

No	Dimension	Variabels
1	Efficient Use of Materials and Environmental Impact Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Monitoring of waste produced in the batik industry environment b. Determination of waste segregation system c. Provision of waste collection points d. Determination of waste reduction system e. Determination of waste reduction and rejection for improper materials system f. Provision of qualification for reject product
2	reduce, reuse, recycled and recovery of material and waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Environment reduce, reuse, recycled of material and waste systems b. Environment recovery of material and waste systems c. Waste management d. Waste analyzed from accredited laboratory
	Storage, Handling and Transport of Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Check the quality of raw materials and primary products after they are received from suppliers. b. Provision of safe storage for hazardous materials. c. Determination of the system of providing the appropriate stock for hazardous materials d. Establishment of a system to avoid loss of raw materials during storage. e. Spill reduction and leakage f. Perfect the way to move and to avoid losing material g. Ensure good ways for cleaning and disposal of hazardous packaging h. Ensure how to avoid losing finished products during storage and transportation
4	Reduction of Water Consumption, Waste water and Pollution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Monitoring water consumption in the batik industry b. Determination of the system reduces water consumption in the production process c. Principle of optimizing water use d. Determination of the system of reuse and or recycle water in the production process e. Establishment of a system to reduce water consumption in the production room. f. Determination of the system to reduce water consumption in non-production parts. g. Determination of ways in waste water is processed in a way that is good in terms of the environment.
5	Reduction of Energy Consumption, Use of Heat and Environmentally Friendly Energy Sources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Monitoring energy consumption in the batik industry b. Reducing energy consumption and costs c. Establish ways to avoid losing energy d. Adequate electrical equipment installed e. Calculation of energy consumption in the

No	Dimension	Variabels
		production process is tailored to the needs. f. Reuse of energy in the production process g. Providing adequate lighting and saving energy
6	Protection against accidents, hazardous materials, odors, noise, vibration and injury	a. Reduction of accident risk b. Procedures to ensure that machines and equipment do not cause risks to employees c. Procedures to ensure that the work environment is safe for employees d. Ease of access to information about hazardous material e. Availability of PPE equipment (personal protection equipment) handling hazardous material is available to employees and well maintained f. prepare for an accident g. Fire reduction h. Reduction of workers' health risks i. Control of air emissions j. Odor pollution control

2.2.1 Place and Time of Research

This research was conducted at the Mantaran batik group and Ayu Arimbi batik group at Sleman Regency. Time of Research This research was conducted in March-July 2018.

2.2.2 Sample research

The population in this study was all group members in the two batik industries who implemented a cleaner production program totaling 50 members from the two batik industry groups. The results of data collection were then analyzed using science. The first stage in science is to determine the level of suitability between the level of importance and the level of performance of the quality dimensions and variables studied through a comparison of performance scores with scores of interests. The suitability level formula used is (Santoso, 2011):

$$T_{ki} = \sum (X_i / Y_i) \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where :

- T_{ki} = level of conformity
- X_i = performance rating score
- Y_i = importance rating score

The second stage is calculating the average for each attribute perceived by consumers, using the formula :

$$X_i = \sum \bar{X}_i / n \quad Y_i = \sum \bar{Y}_i / n \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

- X_i = The average score of the performance level of the batik industry
- Y_i = The Average score of importance on the batik industry
- n = The Quantity of Respondent

Next, the average of all the attributes of importance (Y) and performance (X) are bounded in the Cartesian diagram, using the formula:

$$X = \sum \bar{X}_i / k \quad Y = \sum \bar{Y}_i / k \quad \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where :

X = The average score of the performance level of the batik industry

Y = The Average score of importance on the batik industry

k = Amount of dimensions can affect the performance of implementing cleaner production

The last stage is the elaboration of each attribute in the Cartesian diagram to see a description of the quality of the application of cleaner production for each batik group as shown in Figure 1.

3. Results

Level Analysis of Importance and Performance Analysis (Performance)

After calculating the average answer to the questionnaire used in this study, the next step is to process data and analyze data. Data analysis carried out in this study is to be able to present a collection of measurement data into readable and useful information. The data has been obtained from the results of the respondents' assessment of the importance and performance of each group member towards the implementation of the cleaner production program in the two batik industries above. The level of conformity is the result obtained from a comparison between performance scores and interest scores.

The level of conformity is the result of a comparison between the performance performance score and the interest score, so that it can be used to determine the priority scale (Yola and Duwi, 2013). The level of importance analysis and the average performance of perceptions of each dimension is the basis for determining whether each performance of the implementation of cleaner production in both batik industries is good or not, that is by comparing the average of all attributes (X) and the results of 3.32 The average expectation of each attribute is the basis for determining whether the attribute is important or not important, that is by comparing the average of all attributes (Y) and the results obtained at 4.19 for the batik group Mantaran and X = and Y = for Ayu Arimbibatik group. The mean values of perception and expectation were used to analyze the data in the Cartesian diagram in Figure 2 for the batik transfer group and figure 3 for the ayu Arimbi batik group.

Dimension 1: ○	Dimension 2: △	Dimension 3: ✦	Dimension 4: □	Dimension 5: ◇	Dimension 6: ▭
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Figure 2. IPA Cartesian diagram for Mantaran batik Group

Dimension 1: ○	Dimension 2: △	Dimension 3: ✦	Dimension 4: □	Dimension 5: ◇	Dimension 6: ▭
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Figure 3. IPA Cartesian diagram for Ayu Arimbi Batik Group

Quadrant 1 is a quadrant that has a very low level of satisfaction so it is a top priority for improvement. Of the six dimensions included in quadrant I for the Batik Mantaran group, according to the order of priority levels are the efficiency dimensions of material use and the assessment of environmental impacts especially for recording systems for recording waste and failed products and

the absence of a system to minimize waste. Whereas for the Ayu Arimbi batik group is reduction, reuse, recycling, recovery of waste materials or waste and waste management, especially for the processing of wax recycling and the determination of a good natural dyestuff system and recording.

Quadrant 2 is the quadrant expected by the two batik groups and is in accordance with what is felt by the members of their respective groups. Of the six dimensions in quadrant 2 can also be sorted according to the priority level to be maintained by the Mantaran batik group or Ayu Arimbi batik group has similarities namely storage, handling, and transportation of materials, reduction of water consumption, waste water, and pollution, reduction of energy consumption, heat consumption and environmentally friendly energy sources.

Quadrant 3 is a low priority quadrant because it contains dimensions that are considered less important by the two batik groups and in reality their performance is not too special, namely the order of dimensions according to the priority level to be repaired is protection against accidents, hazardous and toxic materials (B3) odor, noise, vibration and injury.

Both batik groups have similarities in quadrant 4, which does not have a low level of importance, but has a high level of performance.

4. Discussion

In the concept of cleaner production, it is known that understanding about Non-Product Output (NPO) is the first step in conducting analysis before applying the concept of cleaner production itself. NPO is defined as all materials, energy, and water used in the production process but not contained in the final product. NPO forms can be identified in the batik industry, among others, are less quality raw materials in the form of poor quality mori dyes, products that fail because they are not in accordance with the specifications of ordering, reprocessing, solid waste in the form of batik wax, liquid waste (amount of contaminants, overall water not contained in the final product), energy (not contained in final products, such as steam, electricity, oil, diesel, etc.), emissions (including noise and odor), losses due to lack of maintenance and losses due to health and environmental problems, NPO total cost is the sum of NPO costs from inputs, NPO costs from the production process, and NPO costs from output. In general, the total cost of NPO ranges from 10-30% of the total production cost. Therefore it is important for the batik industry to recognize materials sources in the production process in detail, in order to reduce production costs and increase productivity.

Through the results of the IPA calculations of the two batik groups, from the six dimensions it can be concluded that several things that can be used as a reference for corrective actions, especially the variables in the Batik Mantaran group, are dimensions of efficient use of materials and assessment of environmental impacts, especially for recording systems for recording waste and products failed and the absence of a system that was put in place to minimize waste. From these data, it was known the problems faced by the batik industry which are members of the Mantaran batik group and Ayu Arimbi batik group at Sleman Regency, among others, is that there has been no detailed identification and calculation of sources of waste of resources. This is because one component of the resource, for example, water for the production process uses water from Serayu river. Whereas wood as a source of heat energy in release wax (pelorodan) process is available at cheap prices from wood collectors

around it. Although the process of recycled wax with the process of recycled wax collection has been carried out but only limited of being resold to use wax collectors at a price of approximately 30 percent of the price of a fresh wax on the market. The recycled wax process for reuse in the production process has not been done so that because there is no value of production cost savings from recycled wax use so NPO is also dissolved in wastewater. The absence of traps of recycled wax is wax trap (koen). Chemical management has not been carried out optimally by reusing used dyes so that the cost of consuming dye cannot be reduced and increasing the amount of liquid waste used in the coloring process. The environmental load is very large because of the unavailability of waste water treatment plant for good waste treatment.

5. Conclusion

The application of cleaner production is a series of work procedures that are applied at each stage of batik production. The work procedure is expected to result in changes in the mindset and consumption patterns of resources, raw materials and waste management so as to reduce environmental pollution. The results of calculations with the IPA method can be used several variables used as stages of improvement.

It expected for Mantaran batik group and Ayu Arimbi batik group at Sleman Regency can apply the principle of cleaner production continuously so that it gets production efficiency and can reduce production costs also can minimize the potential for environmental pollution and public health.

References

1. Center for Crafts and Batik. *Activity Report*, Yogyakarta, 2017,
2. Bohnet et al. *Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry*, WILEY-VCH, 2010. CBI. *Application of Clean Production in the Batik industry*, KLH, Jakarta, 2010.
3. P. Eimer et al. *Good Internal Management (Good Housekeeping)*, GTZ / P3U, Bonn, 2003.
4. J. Miller. et al. *Chemical Management Guide: Improve Chemical Management to gain Cost Savings, Reduce hazards and Improve Safety*, Revised ed. GTZ., Eschborn, 2003.
5. I. Nastiti Siwi and F. Anas Miftah, *Clean Production*, IPB Press, Bogor, 2009.
6. UNEP .Division of Technology, Industry & Economics, *Environment Agreement and Cleaner Production*, 2007.
7. UNIDO. *Joint UNIDO-UNEP Program on Resource Efficiency and Cleaner Production (RECP)*, 2002
8. Santoso. (2011). *Consumer Perception of the Quality of Telo Bakpao with the Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) Method*. Journal of Agricultural Technology.12 (1)
9. Yola, M dan Budianto, D. (2013). *Analysis of Consumer Satisfaction on Service Quality and Product Prices in Supermarkets Using the Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) Method*. Industrial Systems Optimization Journal. 12 (12) : 301-309.